

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14585661>

THE EFFECT OF THE TASK-BASED INSTRUCTION IN IMPROVING THE ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILLS ON 9th GRADE PUPILS

Qodirova Mavluda Rustamjon qizi

2-course at Namangan State Foreign language Institution, Uzbekistan

Academic advisor: Erqulova Feruza Meliquziyevna (PHD)

Kadirovamavluda007@gmail.com

Abstract: *Due to the challenge of teaching English speaking skills to 5th school students because of large, mixed-ability classes and improper use of available resources, ninth-grade students were used to test the Task-Based Instruction (TBI) approach. Therefore, this article examines how TBI affects ninth-graders' English-speaking abilities and how satisfied they are with the experience using this method. The speaking assessments and the student satisfaction survey were used to gather both quantitative and qualitative data. When comparing the pretest and posttest within the group or the posttests between groups, both quantitative and qualitative analyses showed that the TBI significantly improved the experimental group's speaking abilities overall as well as in each of the subskills. The experimental group was deemed "satisfied" with their experiences with the TBI, according to analyses of the satisfaction questionnaire. In spite of the challenges with the language of instruction, students saw TBI as a method that gave them the right environment for language acquisition, enhanced their speaking abilities, boosted their self-confidence when speaking, and inspired them to learn English.*

Key words: *communicative purpose, TBI (task based instruction), pedagogical approach, proficiency, PPP(presentation, practice and production), speaking competence, experimental group, control group, language focus, language acquisition.*

Introduction

Still, improving speaking in ninth classes is one of the vital sections of learning the English language. Speaking proficiency is classified as one of the most fundamental but difficult productive skills among learners of English as a Second Language (ESL) (Abugohar, Yunus, 2018); TBI is an approach that employs a variety of interactive tasks to engage learners in meaningful communication to achieve communicative purposes, which have gained increasing levels of interest and become the most

fashionable pedagogical approach among foreign language teachers in the past few years (Oxford, 2006; Santos, 2011). Although the effects of the TBI have been studied in detail, insufficient attention has been paid to time as a limitation. The implications of Task-based instruction study deserve to be explored further. It is generally assumed that the previous research only suggested TBI in developing speaking competence; however, this paper suggests a combination of TBI and using computer technology during the lessons. To shape the context for this study, the following research questions were set forward.

1 What is the effect of the TBI in developing ninth graders' speaking skills?

2 To what extent was the TBI method on developing speaking satisfactory for the experimental group pupils?

This paper will first discuss several examples of survey-based research into using TBI in speaking lessons and then will go on to the results and effects of this method.

Methodology

The influences of using TBI in speaking improvement were investigated in his research. The main reason this research theme was selected is that it is less explored, and results are various. This research was studied, and exploring TBI effects in teaching speaking was a common theme for both research projects, but this was explored together with technology to improve pupils' speaking skills more sufficiently. In this research, a mixed type of data was collected as an analysis; in addition to this, primary data was gathered by using real-life experience and experiments. This is action research; that's why it was easy to analyze why it is effective to use TBI in speaking lessons. This exploration was based on pre-, while-, and post-actions and tests in order to analyze the results concisely and comprehensibly. This research was investigated in the fifth school in Chartak, which is one of the regions of Namangan, during a two-week period in November 2024. In the first two lessons, a pretest was organized based on ninth-grade students' textbooks and evaluated according to the IELTS assessment, such as coherence, cohesion, grammar, and lexical resources. The speaking test was divided into three parts. In the first part, pupils were asked personal questions like about hobbies, family, and study. In part 2, which consisted of general questions like favorite actor and childhood, were asked by their partner. In the final part, describing the picture was asked. This speaking structure formed as an interview, and this was face to face. Ninth-grade pupils were divided into 2 groups as there were 26. The first 13 pupils were the experimental group, and the rest were the control group. One pair interview took 12-15 minutes. As it was structured, it did not make it difficult to make conversation with each other. Furthermore, it was recorded by the teacher in order to evaluate after all. The rest of the teachers give an aid to check and mark according to the standards. During the following 4 lessons, I used the TBI method to teach and

develop pupils’ speaking skills. Using technology during the lessons proved more effective rather than ignoring. As a teacher, first I analyze attendance and check the total literal environment of students; after that, I tell the new theme and a task. Showed some real English videos in order to be comprehensible. Then students report the task and check their speech as group work. The teacher highlights main linguistic features, then students themselves practice them. At the end, the teacher marks and gives homework to the pupils. One lesson duration was 45 minutes at school, 3 times in a week. There were six instructional stages: *Opening*, *Pre-Task*, *Task Cycle (1&2)*, *Language Focus*, and *Closing*. Eighteen activities from the English Grade 9 course book were chosen based on Willis’s (2006) criteria, which include a primary focus on meaning, an observable consequence, relevance to students’ needs, and a real-world relationship. The task Cycles’ "tasks." These included seven different sorts of tasks: opinion gap (x4), conversations (x5), listing (x1), ordering (x2), reasoning gap (x2), matching (x3), and information gap (x1). They were selected on the basis of their ability to engage students in the conversations. It necessitated a reciprocal information exchange, potentially facilitating the students’ second language (Ellis, 2000) The control group was taught using the identical course book sections and material but with PPP lesson plans that were created using the three-stage PPP lesson format: Production, Practice, and Presentation Table 1 includes the comprehensive TBI and PPP instructional procedures. The lesson plans were presented to three professionals who taught English language and curriculum. development, as well as evaluation and assessment for examination. These lesson plans included excellent content validity, but certain changes have been made in response to feedback from the example. On the last day of the research, the last interview was organized to analyze any changes in pupils’ speaking skills. However, this time pairs and questions were modified. Students were also asked how the result was for themselves.

TBI	PPP
<p>1 Opening: Teacher does classroom administrative work like, attendance, carry on discipline</p>	<p>1 Presentation: First, teacher teaches -New vocabulary then introduces new topic through texts and dialogues -Highlights linguistic features and check pupils understanding new theme</p>
<p>2 Pre-task:Teacher introduces the new theme and task</p>	<p>2 Practice: Pupils practice new language under control of the teacher</p>
<p>3Task cycle: 3.1 Task: Students do the task themselves</p>	<p>3 Production: Free practice, pupils use target language to produce new data</p>

3.2Planning: pupils get ready for the report	
3.3Report: Pupils present a task report to their classmates in spoken or written forms.	
4Language focus	
4.1Analysis: Teacher highlights vital features from the previous steps	
4.2 Practice: Pupils practice features under control of the teacher	
Closing: The teacher asks questions and assign homework	

Students in the experimental and control groups took the speaking pretests at the start of the experiment. Following that, the experimental group had TBI therapy for nine sessions in a row, and the control group received instruction at the same time, with the same teacher, the researcher, using the conventional PPP approach. The instruction of each group lasted for four and a half weeks, or eighteen hours, following which students received the posttests on speaking.

Discussion and results.

The study demonstrates a correlation between TBI and technology in speaking lessons, showing effective improvement in pupils’ speaking skills during the two-week research. The experimental group’s speaking performance development was significantly impacted by the massive amount of language work that the TBI-taught students had to do individually, in pairs, or in groups. Having been exposed to the task, Students were given the chance to practice communicating their meaning through the language. Additionally, students had to use their language knowledge along with their interaction and communication skills—such as self-correction, rephrasing, repetition, etc.—to convey their meanings through the Task cycles, which required them to complete tasks, plan, and present their reports. In light of this, it can be said that TBI significantly enhanced the students’ overall speaking abilities as well as each of the speaking subskills (fluency, vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, and interaction). The students’ responses indicate that the practice opportunities offered by TBI made it a suitable platform for language development and, as a result, enhanced the students’ speaking abilities. Students could recall more words, employ more proper grammar structures, pronounce words more clearly, speak more confidently and fluently, and engage in conversations more successfully because they were exposed to more real-world language use in each lesson. Students were able to communicate and express their opinions when the teacher used a range of tasks from one session to the next, which kept them interested in the material rather than making them bored. Students’ speaking confidence increased as a result. Additionally, they were more driven to learn

English, so they demanded that their teacher employ TBI going forward. Notwithstanding the advantages, the students also brought up the difficulty with the language of instruction when using TBI for learning. It is important to note at this point that students in the mixed-ability classroom may not have fully understood the instructions given in English rather than their mother tongue because they had different language proficiency levels. For this reason, the students in the TBI classroom complained when the teacher did this. It can be inferred from these explanations that the majority of the experimental group's students were "satisfied" with TBI since it was the approach that could meet their needs and interests while also assisting them in developing their speaking abilities. When students are expected to follow instructions verbally, listening comprehension is also crucial. The results met my expectations positively; the research was able to improve 9th- grade students' speaking skills through TBI and computer technologies. During the research, pupils not only increase their speaking skills but also obstacles like fear to speak and shyness decrease in front of the audience; furthermore, students obtain motivation to study and speak by watching videos during the lessons. The unexpected results had a significant role in pupils' speaking skills. These results build on existing evidence of the previous research. The TBI method was taught during the action research, but together with using technologies in speaking lessons. Consequently, our result was higher than the previous research result. The generalizability of the results is limited by the limitation of the experiment. Only 6 lessons were not enough for the treatment to produce a large development of speaking skills. Future studies should take into account the period to figure out whether it can produce a large effect on pupils' speaking skills.

In the pretest, both experimental and control groups show the same results. However, after the research, the posttest experimental group indicated better results than the control group.

The students' comments indicated that the practice possibilities offered by TBI made it a suitable platform for language development and, as a result, enhanced the students' speaking abilities. Due to the fact that pupils were exposed to more actual language use in each course, they could retain more vocabulary and employ more appropriate grammar rules, pronounce words more clearly, talk more fluidly, and use more. Students were able to discuss and share their thoughts when the teacher used a range of assignments from one session to the next, which simultaneously engaged them in the learning process rather than boring them. Thus, by doing this, the instructor established a calm and encouraging classroom environment, which was essential, particularly for pupils who were less confident to cultivate their inventiveness.

Additionally, through the task cycles, students were expected to apply their language knowledge in conjunction with their interaction and communication skills,

such as self-correction, rephrasing, repetition, etc., in order to complete tasks, plan, and deliver their reports. It is reasonable to assume that these tasks will aid students in enhancing their proficiency. Additionally, the children were exposed to additional language tasks in the Language Focus stage after using their language resources to articulate meanings throughout the task cycles. As a result, the students had more chances to concentrate on linguistic structures that they were previously familiar with, preventing them from developing their fluency at the price of precision.

Appendixes

Pretest Speaking questions in the interview

score/maximum 10

1	What is your hobby?	5
2	Where do you live?	5
3	Who is your best friend?	3
4	Describe your hometown...	2
5	Describe your childhood.....	3
6	Describe time when you regret....	4
7	Who do you want to be in the future?	3
8	How society effects to the youth future?	4

Posttest interview pair

Questions

score/maximum 10

1	What is your hobby?	6
2	Where do you live?	7
3	Who is your best friend?	8
4	Describe your hometown...	5
5	Describe your childhood.....	5
6	Describe time when you regret....	6
7	Who do you want to be in the future?	7
8	How society effects to the youth future?	5

References

- Albino, G. (2017). Improving speaking fluency in a task-based language teaching approach:
The case of EFL learners at PUNIV-Cazenga. *SAGE Open*, 7(2), 1-11.
- Bachman, L. F., & Palmer, A. S. (1996). *Language testing in practice: Designing and developing useful language tests*. Oxford University Press.
- Breen, M. P. (1987). Learner contributions to task design. In C. N. Candlin & D. Murphy (Eds.), *Language learning tasks* (pp. 23-46). NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Bygate, M. (1987). *Language teaching: Speaking*. Oxford University Press.
- Cambridge English. (2011). *Assessing speaking performance: Level A2*. University of Cambridge.
- Canale, M. (1983). From communicative competence to communicative language pedagogy.
In J. Richards & R. Schmidt (Eds.), *Language and communication* (pp. 14-40). London: Routledge.
- Canale, M., & Swain, M. (1980). Theoretical bases of communicative approaches to second language teaching and testing. *Applied Linguistics*. 1(1), 1-47.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/1.1.1>
- Clayton, T. (2006). *Language choice in a nation under transition: English language spread in Cambodia (language policy)*. New York: Springer.
- Coe, R. (2002). *It's the effect size, stupid: What effect size is and why it is important*. Annual Conference of the British Educational Research Association, England.
- Crossman, A. (2019). *Understanding purposive sampling: An overview of the method and its applications*. ThoughtCo. <https://www.thoughtco.com/purposive-sampling-3>
[The Effect of Task-Based Instruction in Improving the English Speaking Skills of Ninth-Graders](https://www.thoughtco.com/purposive-sampling-3)
[Seanghai Nget](https://www.thoughtco.com/purposive-sampling-3)
[Faculty of Education, Naresuan University, Thailand](https://www.thoughtco.com/purposive-sampling-3)
[seanghai61@nu.ac.th](https://www.thoughtco.com/purposive-sampling-3)
[Omthajit Pansri](https://www.thoughtco.com/purposive-sampling-3)
[Faculty of Education, Naresuan University, Thailand](https://www.thoughtco.com/purposive-sampling-3)